

Economic Sustainability in the Textile Industry

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Abstract: Numerous studies and research have taken place across the globe to understand the factors for the economic success of entrepreneurs in various domains. However, the secret of guaranteed success has still not been formulated and found to ascertain the combination of inputs or factors of production to achieve economic sustainability. This paper attempts to put forward an economic concept and its application in the textile industry that entrepreneurs could follow to attain economic sustainability and create a socio-economic impact. The purpose of the study is to identify appropriate production techniques for the weaving process of bedspreads on a wide loom of 60-inch width in the weaving industry in Panipat, Haryana. The study is relevant for all entrepreneurship ventures in any domain. The study is based on the theoretical framework of the concept of PQHR (Physical Quality of Human Resource) and is capable of ascertaining the suitability of a combination of inputs required to achieve an APP (Appropriate Production Path). The study adopted a random sampling technique for sample selection and an interview schedule was administered to the participants for data collection. The sample included the powerloom weaving units of Panipat, Haryana. The data analysis revealed that none of the powerloom weaving units in Panipat, Haryana were following an Appropriate Production Path and thus failed to create a socio-economic impact.

Practical Implications: The study, however, would be able to contribute to and extend the theory of PQHR. It would also be beneficial for entrepreneurs to understand the dynamics of economic sustainability and contribute to society at large by creating a positive socio-economic impact. The study will have long-term practical implications if the framework of the concept of PQHR is applied to every unit of a production process. The input intensities could be monitored and modified to achieve an economically sustainable production process.

Keywords: Powerloom; Production; Socio-economic impact; Sustainability; Textile.

1. Introduction

The textile industry comprises the spinning industry, the weaving industry, the knitting industry, and the apparel industry. The present study confines itself to the weaving industry. It comprises a large unorganized handloom sector scattered almost in every state of India and a small organized powerloom sector which is concentrated in a few places in the country. Though the sector seems to develop and have huge earnings, the entrepreneurs find it difficult to survive and compete in the global scenario. Thus, it can be said that the need of the hour is not only development but sustainable development. To pinpoint the exact problematic areas in the powerloom units and attempt to find a solution for the same, the concept of Physical Quality of Human Resource (PQHR) was applied to the weaving industry.

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The major objective of the study is to identify an appropriate production path for the weaving process of bedspreads on a wide loom of 60-inch width in the weaving industry.

2. Literature Review

The idea of sustainable development, though it may be interpreted differently by various groups and entities, should be incorporated throughout various industries and disciplines. The objective of sustainable development is to decrease the detrimental effects of human actions on the natural world, while simultaneously fostering economic and social progress.

To establish a sustainable community, sustainable development should be viewed as a continual journey rather than a final destination and should serve as the primary perspective for tackling worldwide issues (Robinson, 2004).

Industrial economic activity is one of the primary causes of environmental degradation and a source of issues related to social inequality. Nevertheless, research has shown that the application of the sustainable entrepreneurship model can significantly improve environmental and social conditions while maintaining continuous and sustainable economic growth (Tiuncika & Bormane, 2024).

Sustainable economic growth is the most important goal for governments. Economic growth is also an important part of sustainable economic sustainability. Capital expenditure, which consists of investments in infrastructure, public services, and community development projects, serves as a foundation for economic growth, which impacts productivity, employment, and social welfare. (Zein et al., 2024).

Economic growth is a factor in a country's standing in the global market, but sustainable development ensures that this standing is maintained over time. Sustainable development focuses not only on economic growth, but also on resource abundance, healthy living conditions, and social prosperity within the country (Caiado et al., 2019; Farelnik et al., 2021; Streimikiene & Ahmed, 2021).

During the last seventy years, the strategy of development in India promoted inputs-intensive centralized production processes in select sectors of the economy. This, in turn, has given birth to many socio-economic problems in Indian society, such as widespread unemployment and underemployment, income inequality, poverty, inefficient use of one or the other input/ factor of production, conflict between personal and societal interest and also between the objectives of economic growth and distributive justice. As a result, the entire process of development has become uncompetitive, inefficient, unsustainable, and socially irrelevant (Singh et al., 2004).

Solution of all the above-mentioned socio-economic problems demands a parameter that can integrate the horizontal and vertical dimensions of the concept of development and at the same time can help in regulating the policies and programs related to all the above-mentioned aspects. Realizing the need, Singh (1999) has evolved the concept of Physical Quality of Human Resources (PQHR).

3. Concept of PQHR

The concept of development includes both dimensions - the horizontal dimension representing the objective of distributive justice, as well as the vertical dimension representing the objective of economic growth. Distributive justice means that the fruits of development should be reaped by one and all in the country. In simpler terms, there has to be a balance between economic growth of the nation and distributive justice. Distributive justice demands that the monetary income of every willing worker must be raised to the National Average Money Income per employed and underemployed worker (NAI). This means that there should be no income disparity and each willing worker of the population should have equal money income.

- The monetary income of a worker largely depends upon price structure and labor productivity. Price structure is beyond the scope of the present study.
- *Labor productivity (LP)* is the function of quantity and quality aspects of human efforts put in by the worker for value addition.
- The quantity aspect of human efforts is directly related to the period of gainful employment.
- Quality aspects of human efforts include the level of skill, capital, energy, pollution-free environment, and infrastructure, which the worker possesses and uses.
- Amount/ Quantity/ Level of employment, skill, capital, energy, pollution-free environment, and infrastructural facilities and services per employed and underemployed worker represent the intensity of the concerned input.

- Concerning a worker, production unit, sector of the economy, and national economy as a whole, there are six input intensities. They are as follows:
 - i. Work Intensity (Work Labor Ratio or WLR)
 - ii. Skill Intensity (Skill Labor Ratio or SLR)
 - iii. Capital Intensity (Capital Labor Ratio or CLR)
 - iv. Energy Intensity (Energy Labor Ratio or ELR)
 - v. Pollution Intensity (Pollution Labor Ratio or PLR)
 - vi. Infrastructure Intensity (Infrastructure Labor Ratio or ILR)
- The ratio between the micro-level and macro-level values of input intensities related to the concerned input represents the status of the micro unit, about the corresponding position of the macro unit.
- The product of all six ratios determines the *Physical Quality of Human Resources* (PQHR) of the workers engaged or to be engaged in the production system and also of the production system or micro unit to the macro unit.
- Mathematically,

$$PQHR^* = \frac{WLR_U}{WLR_N} \times \frac{SLR_U}{SLR_N} \times \frac{CLR_U}{CLR_N} \times \frac{ELR_U}{ELR_N} \times \frac{PLR_U}{PLR_N} \times \frac{ILR_U}{ILR_N}$$

Key,

WLR_U	=	Work Labor Ratio at Unit Level
WLR_N	=	Work Labor Ratio at the National Level
SLR_U	=	Skill Labor Ratio at Unit Level
SLR_N	=	Skill Labor Ratio at the National Level
CLR_U	=	Capital Labor Ratio at Unit Level
CLR_N	=	Capital Labor Ratio at the National Level
ELR_U	=	Energy Labor Ratio at Unit Level
ELR_N	=	Energy Labor Ratio at the National Level
PLR_U	=	Pollution Labor Ratio at Unit Level
PLR_N	=	Pollution Labor Ratio at the National Level
ILR_U	=	Infrastructure Labor Ratio at Unit Level
ILR_N	=	Infrastructure Labor Ratio at the National Level

*It may be possible that a particular economic activity does not need one or the other input related to the quality aspects of PQHR. In such a situation, the national level value of the concerned intensity would be taken for the unit level value. This would make the ratio value of the concerned intensity equal to one.

3.1. PQHR as an Indicator

Sustainable development of the weaving industry in Indian conditions requires the identification of sustainable production process/ processes, sustainable limits of the values of different input intensities, and deficiency, if any, in any one or more inputs related to production processes being used in the weaving industry.

- (i) Sustainable production process/ processes
 - (a) Value of PQHR = 1 Sustainable
 - (b) Value of PQHR > 1 Exploitative

(c) Value of PQHR < 1 Unsustainable

A sustainable production process would be one having the value of PQHR equal to one (1), that is, the ratio of inputs used and the labor employed at the unit level in carrying out a production activity is the same as that at the national level. If the ratio of unit-level input intensity and national-level input intensity is more than one, it means that the quantity of inputs utilized at the unit level per worker is much more than that at the national level. In its very basic sense, it would translate into a wastage of resources or inputs.

If the ratio of unit-level input intensity and national-level input intensity is less than one, it means that the concerned input is deficient. Thus, deficiency in any input requires improvement in policies and programs related to the concerned input.

In a nutshell, an increase in the value of PQHR in respect of every willing worker up to one would not only help in achieving the objective of distributive justice but also in accelerating the pace of economic growth, thereby impacting the socio-economic fabric of the society at large.

3.2. Application of the PQHR Concept to the Sugar Industry

The concept of PQHR was successfully applied to the sugar industry by Singh (2000). Various production processes available to manufacture sugar from sugarcane juice were studied. The value of PQHR was then calculated and an Appropriate Production Path was formulated.

3.3. Application of the PQHR Concept to the Apparel Industry

Bawa (2002) applied the concept of PQHR to the apparel industry. The combination of inputs utilized for each step was studied and input intensities were calculated. PQHR was then calculated and an Appropriate Production Path was identified.

4. Methodology

To realize the objectives of the study, data was collected at the unit level and national level. The Weaving Industry supplied the primary data, whereas secondary data about the national-level values of the above-mentioned parameters was collected by referring to various published and unpublished reports of both government and non-government organizations.

The study was carried out in the Panipat district of Haryana state of India. Panipat was selected as the locale for the study as it is considered a major weaving hub of the country. The sample was selected in a comprehensive way to include the weaving units at varying levels of technology. It was decided to survey units with both conventional looms and advanced shuttleless looms. A sample size of 100 units was chosen from these lists. An interview schedule was formulated and administered to the entrepreneurs of the weaving units.

5. Analysis

The data thus collected was tabulated, consolidated, statistically analyzed, and presented. The use of statistical measures varied with the nature of the data. Qualitative analysis was also done for responses to open-ended questions.

5.1. Work Labor Ratio

Table 1. Work Labor Ratio (WLR)

S. No.	Type of unit	Work Labor Ratio (WLR)
1.	Conventional loom units	1.2
2.	Rapier loom units	1.2
3.	Air-jet loom units	1.2

It is indicated from **Table 1** that the Work Labor Ratio (WLR) is greater than 1 for all three types of units. It stands at 1.2 for all the three types of units. This implies that there is an overutilization or exploitation of the workers in all three types of units.

5.2. Skill Labor Ratio

Table 2. Skill Labor Ratio (SLR)

S. No.	Type of unit	Skill Labor Ratio (SLR)
1.	Conventional loom units	0.36
2.	Rapier loom units	1.02
3.	Air-jet loom units	1.03

As can be seen from **Table 2**, the Skill Labor Ratio (SLR) i.e., the average skill level per person for performing a particular function is the highest for air-jet loom units at 1.03. It is the lowest at 0.36 for conventional loom units. This means that the skill required for performing any function increases with the use of machines and the level of automation.

5.3. Capital Labor Ratio

Table 3. Capital Labor Ratio (CLR)

S.No.	Type of unit	Capital Labor Ratio (CLR)
1.	Conventional loom units	131380.25
2.	Rapier loom units	3635520.81
3.	Air-jet loom units	4759735.94

As can be seen from **Table 3**, the fixed capital, as well as the Capital Labor Ratio (CLR), is the lowest for the conventional loom units at 131380.25. The value is the highest for air-jet loom units at 4759735.94. Since the cost of a conventional loom is the lowest among the three types of looms, the CLR is the lowest for these types of units.

5.4. Energy Labor Ratio

Table 4. Energy Labor Ratio (ELR)

S.No.	Type of unit	Energy Labor Ratio (ELR)
1.	Conventional loom units	5745.55
2.	Rapier loom units	62737.14
3.	Air-jet loom units	29803.28

Energy was utilized to run the machines and equipment in the weaving units. All types of weaving units were highly dependent on electricity availability as all of them had looms operated by power. **Table 4** puts forward the electricity units utilized by the units and the Energy Labor Ratio (ELR).

5.5. Pollution Labor Ratio

Table 5. Pollution Labor Ratio (PLR)

S.No.	Type of unit	Pollution Labor Ratio (PLR)
1.	Conventional loom units	0.057
2.	Rapier loom units	0.311
3.	Air-jet loom units	0.098

The noise pollution in the units was measured using a Noise Level Meter. **Table 5** presents the information regarding the Pollution Labor Ratio (PLR).

5.6. Standards for Industrial Noise

The damage risk criteria for hearing as enforced by ISO DGMS (through its circular no. DG (Tech)/ 18 of 1975) and CPCB stipulate that noise levels up to 90 dB are acceptable for 8 hours of exposure per day. That is 90 dB is the maximum sound level, to which an employee can be exposed for 8 hours on a given working day.

Several processes in the textile industry, especially spinning and weaving produce noise of the order of 90 dB (A). The noise pollution created by the weaving units is apparent in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Noise Level in the textile industry

S.No.	Section/ Operation	Noise Level [dB (A)]*
1.	Blow room	85 – 94
2.	Carding	87 – 90
3.	Spinning	89 – 96
4.	Winding	85 – 89
5.	Weaving	90 – 96

Source: Comprehensive Industry Documents Series: COINDS/59/1999-2000, Central Pollution Control Board, Ministry of Environment & Forests, Govt. of India. *dB (A) denotes the time-weighted average of the level of sound in decibels.

5.7. Infrastructure Labor Ratio

Table 7. Infrastructure Labor Ratio (ILR)

S.No.	Type of unit	Infrastructure Labor Ratio (ILR)
1.	Conventional loom units	13138.02
2.	Rapier loom units	363552.08
3.	Air-jet loom units	475973.59

The infrastructure cost incurred by the units was calculated as 10% of the fixed capital invested in the units. **Table 7** puts forward the information regarding the Infrastructure Labor Ratio (ILR).

5.8. Inputs at the National Level

Table 8 presents the data about all inputs at the national level. The data related to pollution, however, was not available in the secondary sources. So, further analysis concerning the Pollution Labor Ratio (PLR) could not be done.

Table 8. Inputs at the national level

S.No.	Input	National
1.	Labor (Man years)	419650000
2.	Work level (Man years)	419650000 x 1
3.	Skill	152500810
4.	Capital (Rs.)	1494631 x 10 ⁷
5.	Energy (KWHr)	393330 x 10 ⁶
6.	Pollution (Decibel)	Not available
7.	Infrastructure (Rs.)	1494631 x 10 ⁶
8.	GDP (Rs.)	4283040 x 10 ⁷

Sources:

1. 2004 – 2005 figures by Planning Commission, Economic Survey 2007 – 2008, p. 247, Govt. of India.
2. 2004 – 2005 figures by Planning Commission, Economic Survey 2007 – 2008, p. 247, Govt. of India and NSS 55th Round. One man year denotes 2400 working hrs. Per year.

3. Unpublished doctoral thesis, Singh, Satbir (2000), Systems Approach to Resource Planning: A case study of sugarcane processing in India, IIT Delhi, 1999, p. 140 and secondary data.
4. 2005 – 2006 figures, Statistical Outline of India, 2007 – 08, Tata Services Limited, p.27.
5. 2005 – 2006 figures, Statistical Outline of India, 2007 – 08, Tata Services Limited, p.77.
6. Not available.
7. 10% of capital.
8. 2006 – 2007 figures, Statistical Outline of India, 2007 – 08, Tata Services Limited, p.01.

5.9. Input Intensities at the National Level

As per the values of inputs at the national level, input intensities were calculated at the national level and the data is presented in **Table 9**.

Table 9. Input Intensities at the national level

S.No.	Input	National
1.	WLR (man year)	1.15
2.	SLR	0.363
3.	CLR (Rs.)	35616.13
4.	ELR (KWHr)	937.281
5.	PLR (Decibel)	NA
6.	ILR (Rs.)	3561.61
7.	OLR (Rs.)	102060.00

OLR refers to the National Average Income (NAI), which should be earned by an employed worker.

5.10. Input Intensities in the Weaving Industry

The production of a fabric by the process of weaving is carried out on a loom. The steps followed in the process of weaving have been classified into

- a. Shedding
- b. Picking
- c. Beating in
- d. Taking up and letting off

All the above-mentioned steps are carried out on a particular type of loom. As it is not possible to carry out one step on one type of loom and the next step on any other loom, the type of loom was considered an individual production process. The value of PQHR was thus calculated for the three production processes that were available in the population.

To calculate the value of PQHR, the input intensities had to be calculated first for the unit-level data. The data regarding input intensities have been presented in an earlier part of this paper and are being reproduced for ready reference under Table 10 as comprehensive data.

Table 10. Input intensities in the weaving industry

Input Intensity	Conventional loom units	Rapier loom units	Air jet loom units
WLR	1.2	1.2	1.2
SLR	0.36	1.02	1.03
CLR	131380.25	3635520.81	4759735.94
ELR	5745.55	62737.14	29803.28
PLR	0.057	0.311	0.098
ILR	13138.02	363552.08	475973.59

The data presented in **Table 10** clearly shows that there was a very wide difference in the values of the input intensities for the three types of loom units.

5.11. Appropriateness of Production Processes in the Weaving Industry

Based on the input intensities presented in Table 9 and Table 10, PQHR values for the three production processes were computed and are stated in **Table 11**.

Table 11. Unit and national level values of PQHR

Input Intensity Ratio	Conventional loom units	Rapier loom units	Air jet loom units	National
WLR _U /WLR _N	1.04	1.04	0.04	1
SLR _U /SLR _N	0.99	2.81	2.84	1
CLR _U /CLR _N	3.69	102.07	133.64	1
ELR _U /ELR _N	6.13	66.93	31.80	1
PLR _U /WLR _N	NA	NA	NA	NA
ILR _U /ILR _N	3.69	102.07	133.64	1
PQHR	85.94	2037777.27	1677458.30	1

U – Unit level, N – National level

Table 11 implies that the value of PQHR for none of the three production processes is neither equal to 1 nor falls in the acceptable range of $1 \pm 20\%$. Hence, none of the three types of production processes used in the weaving industry, namely conventional looms, rapier looms and air-jet looms, satisfy the criteria to be termed as APP.

6. Discussions

Formulation and adoption of APP are possible if and only if indigenous technology is used in the country which would decrease the capital cost, energy consumption, and infrastructure cost as well. The decrease in the values of capital, energy, and infrastructure should be compensated by an increase in the skill level of the workers. This would ensure that the rate of production is not lowered on one hand, and the quality is maintained on the other. Consequently, the entire process of weaving would become sustainable in the long run. This, in turn, would impact the socio-economic status of the weaving industry.

7. Conclusion

The results show that the capital invested in the units per worker is very high compared to the national average values. In other words, huge investments had been made in the 100 weaving units because of the high cost of the weaving equipment. Since a majority of the operations were performed by automatic machines, it decreased the number of labor employed in the units. The present situation has worsened the problem of rampant unemployment in the country. Thus, in the social interest of the country and to create a positive socio-economic impact, one needs to follow a middle path of modernization to an extent that the number of laborers employed does not become negligible because the society as a whole will benefit not from ‘Mass Production’ but from ‘Production by Masses’.

7.1. Future Studies

If the APP had been adopted by the 100 surveyed weaving units, it would have resulted in a decrease in the amount of inputs utilized.

Investment Planning should be thus carried out to distribute the inputs among different units of a sector and different sectors of the economy as per the APP. Research and Development should make the identified APP technically feasible. The HRD should work at all levels to produce manpower of the required quality and quantity.

If APP is adopted by every unit of every sector of the economy, there would be a saving in the amount of inputs utilized which can be used by the unemployed people in the country. Therefore, the study recommends applying the concept of PQHR to various units in different sectors of the economy.

This process would continue to raise the level of employment and national average income and solve the problems of inefficient and non-competitive use of the inputs, inequality in income distribution, unemployment and underemployment, poverty, and also population growth faced by the Indian society as a whole.

7.2. Limitations of the Study

The application of the concept of PQHR can identify an Appropriate Production Path by ascertaining the inputs utilized at the unit level and the national level. However, in case of secondary data not being available for any particular input utilized at the national level, the input intensity cannot be calculated which limits the identification of the amount of input that should be utilized for an Appropriate Production Path.

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